

Effects of high performance work practices on job performance in project-based organisations

V. Wickramasinghe

S. Liyanage

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

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Abstract

This paper investigates high performance work practices used in project-based globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka and their effect on job performance. A random sample of 220 employees engaged full-time in globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka responded. For the data analysis, descriptive statistics, factor analysis, correlation analysis, and multiple regression were used. Three main high performance work practices were identified by the analysis, namely, performance evaluation, learning and development, and involvement in decision making. These three practices significantly positively predict job performance of employees attached to project-based globally distributed software development firms.

Key words: Globally distributed software development; High performance work practices, Human resource management, Project-based organisations

Introduction

Organisations with project-based work structures have intensified in recent years to respond to highly differentiated and customised nature of demand in certain industries such as creative and cultural, high technology, and professional and consulting industries (Davenport, 2006; Sydow, Lindkvist, & DeFillippi, 2004; Turner & Keegan, 1999; Turner, Huemann, & Keegan, 2008). In general, a project-based work organisation defines management by projects as its organisational strategy, applies projects and programmes for the performance of complex processes, manages a project portfolio of different internal and external project types, and perceives itself as being project-oriented (Turner et al., 2008). Hence, project-based work organisations adopt temporary work structures and associated temporary work processes to deliver products and services to its customers (Turner et al., 2008).

The literature identifies project-based work organisations as an organisational innovation, which may influence both technical and social system of the organisation

through new structures, methods, technical systems, and behavioural patterns (Martinsuo et al., 2006). The success of a project-based organisation very much depends on its knowledge workers' capabilities to develop new skills and apply old skills in novel ways (Davenport, 2006). Therefore, the project management literature suggests that human resource management (HRM) practices adopted by these organisations should support the project-based work environment (Huemann, Keegan, & Turner, 2007; Turner et al., 2008; Zupan & Kaše, 2007). In this regard, the HRM literature classifies some of the HRM practices (such as employee involvement and information sharing) as high performance work practices (HPWPs) (Gollan, 2005; Long & Shields, 2005; Marchington 2001; Wood, 1996). These HPWPs represent soft HRM best practices that promote mutual influence, mutual respect and mutual responsibility at the workplace (Gollan, 2005; Long & Shields, 2005; Marchington 2001; Wood, 1996). High performance work practices are very much relevant to project-based organisations as these propagate jobs to be designed broader combined with planning and implementation, individual job responsibilities to be changed as environmental conditions change, teams to be made accountable for performance, and control and lateral co-ordination are to be based on shared goals with minimum status differences (Gollan et al., 2005).

For several reasons, a study on the effects of HPWPs in project-based organisations is important. First, although HRM is a core process that influence how human resource is acquired and deployed for the survival and growth (Turner et al., 2008), a limited amount of research has considered HRM strategies in project-based organisations (Bryde & Wright, 2007; Chiesa et al., 2007; Huemann et al., 2007; Kloppenborg & Opfner, 2002; Ratcheva, 2009; Themistocleous & Wearne, 2000). Specifically, we were unable to find empirical studies conducted in project-based software development firms that investigated HPWPs designed to improve employee performance, which in turn would increase organisational performance. Hence, there is a gap in the project management literature as well as the HRM

literature on human resource dynamics of project-based organisations (Huemann et al., 2007).

Second, valuable lessons could be learned from experiences in different industrial sectors in different parts of the world. The current study was conducted in the globally distributed software development sector in Sri Lanka. In response to increasing global competition many organisations in the U.S., Europe and the Asia Pacific are locating their research and development centres overseas or sending their programming, engineering, and technical back office work overseas to take the advantage of lower costs and broader talent pools around the world. As a consequence, many software products, components, and custom-designed systems are created in globally distributed teams in the South Asia, China, Southeast Asia, Russia, Eastern Europe, and Latin America (Cusumano, 2008). A globally distributed software development project team is a network of dispersed group of people who work together toward a common goal and who share together resources, know-how, services, and by-products (Bourgault et al., 2008; Reed and Knight, 2010). These project teams are made up of members with complementary skills (Blankenship & Ruona, 2009) and team members are selected by the management to work together to complete a specific project or task such as to create a new product or to solve a problem (Wenger & Snyder, 2000). Further, these temporarily assigned members typically come from different national, ethnic, functional and educational backgrounds, reside in different countries or continents with different time zones, and rarely or never see each other in person (Cusumano, 2008; Kankanhalli et al., 2006; Kotlarsky and Oshri, 2005; Reed and Knight, 2010). Yet, they work together interdependently and use ICT to communicate and coordinate their time-constrained project tasks (Bourgault et al., 2008; Peters and Karren, 2009). This globally distributed software development sector is reputed for the use of project teams to achieve desired results. However, previous empirical studies continue to provide evidence of poor success rates in project-based software development projects (Jewels & Ford, 2006) and suggest the importance of better understanding of how to manage project-

based software development project teams to increase the chances of success (Faraj & Sproull, 2000).

In the above context, the focus of this paper is to discuss results of an empirical investigation on HPWPs used in the project-based globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka. The specific questions examined in this paper are what are the HPWPs used in the project-based globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka?, and to what extent HPWPs play a significant role in enhancing job performance of employees? Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the article reviews briefly the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Literature review and hypotheses

The HRM literature on universalistic theories of HRM and performance linkage identifies a set of HRM best practices that leads to improve an organization's performance (Boselie, Dietz, & Boon, 2005; Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Ngo, Lau, & Foley, 2008; Pfeffer, 1998). These HRM best practices are also known as HPWPs (Geringer, Frayne, & Milliman, 2002; Gollan, 2005; Long & Shields, 2005; Marchington 2001; Wood, 1996). Previous studies suggest that HPWPs include but not limited to the practices of performance management (Delery & Doty, 1996; Ketkar & Sett, 2009), training (Boselie et al., 2005; Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Luna & Camps, 2008), rewards (Pfeffer, 1998; Geringer et al., 2002; Luna & Camps, 2008), recruitment and selection (Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Pfeffer, 1998), participation (Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Mohr & Zoghi, 2008), leadership (Geringer et al., 2002), and information sharing (Baptiste, 2008; Boselie et al., 2005). Further, the literature suggests that the impact of HPWPs on employees and organisations are higher if those are implemented as a bundle of practices than in isolation

(Gould-Williams, 2004; Guest, 1998; Guest et al., 2003). Yet, there is little consensus about which bundle of practices should be implemented (Baptiste, 2008; Guest, 1998).

The objectives of introducing HPWPs to an organisation are performance improvement and cost efficiency by building employee satisfaction and commitment through greater employee involvement and participation (Gollan, 2005). Previous research provides evidence for the use of HPWPs in different contexts (such as Fabling & Grimes, 2010; Guest et al., 2003; Ngo et al., 2008). For instance, Guest et al (2003) in their study of HPWPs in UK companies identified 48 practices that were broadly categorized into nine main areas of HPWPs including training and development and performance appraisal. Previous research provides evidence that HPWPs achieve higher levels of performance in the contexts of United States and United Kingdom (Appelbaum et al., 2000; Macky & Boxall, 2008; Patterson et al. 1997). For instance, Patterson et al. (1997) found that practices such as performance appraisal, training and development, and team working have significant positive effect on productivity. Macky and Boxall (2008) found positive relationship between HPWPs and employee job satisfaction. Further, Macky and Boxall (2008, p. 50) conclude that in situations where employees' experience of knowledge, information, rewards and power increases, the employment relationship moves in a direction that employees find more satisfying. Ngo et al. (2008) and Bjorkman and Fan (2002) investigated the use of HPWPs in China and found that HPWPs have direct positive effect on financial performance and operational performance. Further, Fabling and Grimes (2010) investigated the use of HPWPs in New Zealand and found that HPWPs have a causal effect on firm outcomes. Furthermore, Katou and Budhwar (2007) found that recruitment, training, promotion, incentives, benefits, and involvement are positively related to organizational performance in the Greek context. In addition, Sels et al. (2006) investigated the existence of HPWPs in small businesses in Belgium and provide evidence that HPWPs leads to enhance small businesses' productivity and profitability.

Although majority of previous studies provide evidence that HPWPs positively related to organizational performance, few qualitative studies provide evidence that employees often confronted with greater job responsibilities and work pressure once HPWPs are introduced, and they respond positively only when increases in job responsibilities do not come with an increase in stress and strain (Mackie, Holahan, & Gottlieb, 2001; Godard, 2004). For instance, Macky and Boxall (2008, p. 38) provide evidence that in situations where organisational pressures to work longer hours are higher and the organisation places stronger demands on personal time, employees are likely to experience greater dissatisfaction with their jobs, higher levels of stress and fatigue, and a greater work–life imbalance. Because of such findings, Godard (2004) suggests that although HPWPs may be highly effective in some workplaces, in some other workplaces HPWPs may result in more negative organisational outcomes. Therefore, the literature suggests that the implications of HPWPs for employees and organisations are at best uncertain (Godard, 2004), and additional robust and quantitative evidence are needed to support the HPWPs - performance link (Ericksen & Dyer, 2005; Wright, Snell, & Dyer, 2005).

The present study investigated the effect of HPWPs on employees attached to global software development industry in Sri Lanka, which is well recognised to use project-based management structures. Due to the inherent nature of this industry we identify HPWPs as very important. For instance, the majority of the firms have about two layers in the organisational hierarchy (i.e. top management and technical specialists) and opportunities for promotion are few and far between (Wickramasinghe, 2009). Employees feel loss of interest in their jobs and tend to leave present workplaces creating high labour turnover in the industry. Job satisfaction of employees who hop from one workplace to the other tends to be higher compared with those who remain with one employer; employees who hop from one workplace to another may have a small number of years of experience in their present workplaces although they may have several years of service in the industry as a whole (Wickramasinghe, 2009). The literature in general on project-based organisations also

identifies the problems of knowledge retention and transfer (Bresnen, Goussevskaia, & Swan, 2004; Davenport, 2006). In this regard, Lawler III (2005) suggest that organisations need to develop a relationship with employees that stresses continued employment based on performance and having the right skill set to achieve business objectives, where people are rewarded for performance and skill development (Lawler III, 2005). According to Gollan et al. (2005), HPWPs could provide a platform in this regard and create success for organisations as well as employees.

Further, Gollan (2005, p. 20) suggests that in an environment of greater non-union employee relations HPWPs can be identified as an alternative institutional arrangement for employees to have a “voice” in the workplace through greater participation and involvement. In the Sri Lankan context, employees in the global software development industry as well as in many other emerging business sectors are not unionized. Although the non-existence of trade unions is a prerequisite for successful performance in increasingly competitive domestic and international markets (Gollan, 2005), employee satisfaction with the management and commitment can only be created if the participation and involvement of employees is sought by implementing HPWPs (Campling & Gollan, 1999).

Furthermore, the literature suggests that it is difficult to isolate the effects of HPWPs at the organisational level due to intangible nature of outcomes of HPWPs as well as long timeframe required to show any efficiency gains (Gollan, 2005). Therefore, in the present study, the effects of HPWPs on job performance are investigated. Previous studies conducted in project-based globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka provide evidence that these firms highly emphasise the individual-based component in skill training, incentives, and performance evaluation over the team-based component (Wickramasinghe & Mahahettige, 2011). Therefore, for the study, job performance was conceptualised as the individual job performance. In this regard, on the one hand, Saks (2006) argue if individual level constructs (e.g. HPWPs) lead to group or business level results, it must first impact on individual-level outcomes in terms of individuals' attitudes,

intentions, and behaviours. On the other hand, Boxall and Macky (2007) identify chain of links between HRM and performance, namely, intended HRM practices lead to actual HRM practices, which lead to perceived HPWPs, and then to employee reactions, and, finally, to organisational performance. Because of these links, Boxall and Macky (2007) argue that the relationship between HPWPs and organisational performance can be improved by incorporating employee beliefs, attitudes and behaviours. In this regard, the project management literature also emphasises the importance of investigating the perspective of the individual employee as the majority of research on HPWPs in project-based organisations were undertaken from managerial and prescriptive perspectives (Huemann et al., 2007). Therefore, we considered individual job performance as the outcome variable.

Perceived HPWPs are considered as the independent variable for the study. Our preliminary investigations in the project-based globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka led to suggest that performance evaluation, learning and development, and employees' involvement in decision making are the most common HPWPs used in the industry. Therefore, our study was confined to investigate whether performance evaluation, learning and development, and employees' involvement in decision making influence job performance in knowledge intensive project-based organisations.

When considering specific HPWPs of performance evaluation, learning and development, and employees' involvement in decision making, the literature provides evidence that these three HPWPs are positively related to performance. Previous research provides evidence that performance evaluation practices positively related to performance (Geringer et al., 2002; Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Sels et al., 2006; Singh, 2004; Delery & Doty, 1996). Performance evaluation is about the development and motivation of employees by identifying important areas that are important to the job performance of individuals and assessing how well they are performing their jobs (Sels et al., 2006). In this regard, Sels et al. (2006) suggest the importance of using a transparent appraisal procedure in creating perceptions of justice. Paul and Anantharaman (2004) also provide evidence that

performance appraisal is a highly used practice in software development firms in India. Further, previous research provides evidence that learning and development practices positively related to performance (Evans & Davis, 2005; Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Luna & Camps, 2008; Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Geringer et al., 2002). The literature emphasises that learning and development practices that put a premium on development of new skills and learning abilities enhance organisational flexibility by building broader repertoires of skills and behaviours possessed by the employees (Collins & Smith 2006). Paul and Anantharaman (2004) also provide evidence that continuous employee development is a highly used practice in software development firms in India. Furthermore, previous research provides evidence that practices used to involve employees in decision making positively related to performance (Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Mohr & Zoghi, 2008; Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Pfeffer, 1998). Teamwork and delegation creates a culture in which people at all levels of the organization are willing and able to participate in decision making to improve their job performance and increase efficiency, and be more responsive to customer needs (Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Mohr & Zoghi, 2008). Therefore, based on the literature reviewed above that suggests positive relationships between performance evaluation (Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Sels et al., 2006; Singh, 2004), learning and development (Evans & Davis, 2005; Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Sels et al., 2006), and employees' involvement in decision making (Ketkar & Sett, 2009; Mohr & Zoghi, 2008) and job performance, it is proposed for the study:

H1: High performance work practices relating to performance evaluation positively influence job performance.

H2: High performance work practices relating to learning and development positively influence job performance

H3: High performance work practices that lead to involve employees in decision making positively influence job performance

The conceptual model developed for the study is shown in Figure 1.

Take in Figure I

Methodology

Sample

The study was conducted in the project-based globally distributed software development sector in Sri Lanka. For the study, firms with more than 300 employees were selected. This restriction on the number of employees was imposed to eliminate small firms where specific HRM practices are not explicit. The study was conducted using the survey methodology. A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode of data collection. A contact person was identified at each firm to distribute the survey questionnaire. Contact persons were instructed to randomly identify people employed full-time as software development project team members whose main job function is development and maintenance of a software product from his/her firm. One of the authors of this article and contact persons randomly selected the individuals who were directly involved in developing and maintaining a software product from each project team and distributed the questionnaire. Of the 350 questionnaires sent out, 220 valid responses were returned, yielding a response rate of 63% of the original sample. The characteristics of the sample are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table I

Measures

All the variables were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). For all measurement scales, Cronbach's alpha was examined and principal components factor analysis (varimax rotation) was conducted. The

criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7. The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct.

Job performance was measured by the four items from Rodwell, Kienzle, & Shadur (1998). To measure HPWPs, 14 items were developed based on the preliminary inquiries made during the study and from the literature reviewed earlier (such as Boxall & Macky, 2007; Geringer et al., 2002; Gollan et al., 2005; Luna & Camps, 2008; Macky & Boxall, 2008). These items were developed adhering to the guidelines recommended by Nunnally (1978). In doing so, first, the domain of the relevant construct was specified. Then, items were developed to map the construct's conceptual definition.

The literature suggests that individuals' perceptions may vary by their demographic characteristics, such as age and firm specific characteristics such as firm size (in terms of the number of employees) (e.g., Fraizer et al., 2004). Therefore, five individual demographic characteristics (age, gender, the highest level of education, the years of experience in the present workplace, and the total years of work experience) and three firm level characteristics (the number of employees, the years of industry presence, and the existence of HR department) were controlled in the analysis. In other words, in evaluating the effect of HPWPs on job performance, the study controlled for eight demographic variables that could affect job performance. By holding these variables constant, the analysis could isolate whether there actually is a relationship between the level of HPWPs and job performance making the findings more powerful and "true". Therefore, to assess the effect of control variables, these eight control variables were entered as the first step of the regression equation, followed by the predictor variables of HPWPs in the subsequent step. A statistical test of the change in R^2 from the first stage is used to evaluate the importance of HPWPs in predicting job performance. In the analysis, gender was coded as female = 0, male = 1; the highest level of education was coded as graduate = 0, postgraduate = 1; age was coded as

between 20 to 30 = 0, 31 to 40 =1, and the existence of HRM department was coded as no = 0, yes =1. The number of employees in the present workplace was log transformed. The values for the work experience of individuals and the industry presence of the firms were measured in years.

Methods of data collection and analysis

The study was conducted using the survey methodology. A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode of data collection. Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in the English language. As detailed in the section on *measures*, the questionnaire comprised of three sections. Section one inquired about HPWPs. As detailed in the section on *measures*, the 14 items about HPWPs were on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Section two inquired about individual job performance. As detailed in the section on *measures*, the four items on individual job performance were on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Section three inquired about five individual demographic characteristics and three firm level characteristics. As detailed in the section on *measures*, the five individual demographic characteristics inquired in the questionnaire were gender, the highest level of education, the years of experience in the present workplace, and the total years of work experience. As detailed in the section on *measures*, three firm level characteristics inquired in the questionnaire were the number of employees in the workplace, the years of industry presence, and the existence of HR department. The self-administered survey questionnaire was pre-tested with a random sample that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution.

When self-report measures from a single source are used to evaluate variables, the literature highlights the problem of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Spector, 1994). However, Spector (1994) suggests that despite the weaknesses of the cross-

sectional self-report methodology, this design can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to jobs and for deriving hypotheses. Therefore, procedural and statistical measures were taken to reduce common method bias in the current study. First, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension (a procedure recommended by Podsakoff et al., 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to conduct Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003). For the data analysis, descriptive statistics and multiple regression were used.

Results and discussion

The first research question examined in this paper is what are the HPWPs used in the project-based globally distributed software development firms in Sri Lanka. To identify the specific HPWPs used in the project-based globally distributed software development firms, following procedure was used. First, the 14-item HPWPs measure was subjected to reliability analysis. The 14-item HPWPs measure had a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.865. Second, in the attempt to identify the underlying dimensions as perceived by respondents, exploratory factor analysis was conducted. Therefore, in the study, factor analysis (with Varimax rotation) was used as a data reduction technique to identify factors that underlie 14-items of HPWPs for the use in subsequent regression analysis. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues should be greater than 1; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be .0.7. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test statistics were calculated. The KMO statistic was above the customary reference point of 0.5 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant – associated probability was less than the customary reference point of 0.05 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed (for detailed explanations of statistical analysis please refer to Hair et

al., 2006). Table 2 summarises the results of factor analysis. Factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 67% (66.95) of the variance. Factor 1 was labelled as “performance evaluation”, Factor 2 as “learning and development”, and Factor 3 as “involvement in decision making”. Therefore, the results of factor analysis revealed that 14-item measure of HPWPs can broadly be classified into three factors. In other words, the results of factor analysis revealed that HPWPs used in the project-based globally distributed software development firms can broadly be classified into three areas. According to the results of the factor analysis these three areas are performance evaluation, learning and development, and involvement in decision making. This answers to our first research question, i.e., what are the HPWPs used in the project-based globally distributed software development firms.

Take in Table 2

Same procedure was used to identify underlying factors of job performance. Factor analysis yielded one factor. Table 3 shows the results relating to job performance.

Take in Table 3

The means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations for the study variables are shown in Table 4. As can be seen in Table 4, correlations between the three HPWPs and job performance are positive and significant. Correlation analysis reveals that correlations between independent variables are low suggesting low collinearity while correlations between independent variables and dependent variable are high suggesting better prediction in the regression analysis.

Take in Table 4

To answer our second research question, i.e., to what extent do HPWPs play a significant role in enhancing job performance, regression analysis was used. Results are summarised in Table 5.

Take in Table 5

To interpret the results of data analysis, we used beta coefficient (β), coefficient of determination (R^2), and adjusted coefficient of determination (adjusted R^2). The beta coefficient allows for a direct comparison between coefficients as to their relative explanatory power of the dependent variable, i.e., job performance. Coefficient of determination provides a measure of the proportion of the variance of the dependent variable that is explained by independent variables. Adjusted coefficient of determination provides the measure by taking into account the number of predictor variables and the number of observations in the model.

As can be seen in Table 5, control variables are not significant in predicting job performance (Adj. $R^2 = .009$, $p > 0.05$). The adjusted R^2 of 0.415 reveal that final model explained 42% of the variance in job performance ($p < 0.001$). The inclusion of three main independent variables into the model resulted in 44% of the variance being explained (R^2 Change = 0.435). In other words, the main variables of performance evaluation, learning and development, and involvement in decision making alone explained 44% of the variability of job performance (R^2 Change = 0.435, $p < 0.001$). Factor 1, performance evaluation, has a significant positive effect on job performance ($\beta = 0.308$, $p < 0.001$). This supports H1. Factor 2, learning and development, has a significant positive effect on job performance ($\beta = 0.385$, $p < 0.001$). This supports H2. Factor 3, involvement in decision making has a significant positive effect on job performance ($\beta = 0.318$, $p < 0.001$). This supports H3. As detailed

above, beta coefficients allow for a relative assessment of each independent variable's importance in the regression model. Although beta coefficients of performance evaluation, learning and development, and involvement in decision making are not very large, all these three variables have a substantial impact in our overall regression model (for interpretation, refer to Hair et al., 2006, p. 268). Overall, the results of the regression analysis provide evidence that the three HPWPs play a significant role in enhancing job performance. Therefore, findings shown in Table 5 support the hypotheses set for the study.

Table 6 summarises the results of all hypotheses tested.

Take in Table 6

Conclusions and implications

While it is recognised the importance of HPWPs for project-based organisations in the present business environment, the literature provides little empirical evidence on the impact of HPWPs on employees and organisations. Drawing on a random sample of employees full-time attached to the global software development industry in Sri Lanka the study examined the effect of HPWPs on job performance. The novel character of this research is that it investigated several HPWPs which are not given due attention in the literature on project-based organisations.

The first objective of the study was to identify HPWPs used in the project-based globally distributed software development firms. It was found that three distinct HPWPs are used in the industry, namely, performance evaluation, learning and development, and involvement in decision making. Project-based organisations adopt temporary organisations in the form of projects and programmes, and associated temporary work processes to deliver its products and services to its customers (Turner et al., 2008). In this context, performance evaluation, learning and development, and involvement in decision making could be identified as important HPWPs used by these organisations. The second objective

of the study was to investigate to what extent HPWPs play a significant role in enhancing job performance of employees. It was found that all the three HPWPs have significant positive effect on job performance. The literature on project-based organisations suggests the importance of the ability of employees to develop new skills and apply old skills in novel ways to be innovative and to face unstable market conditions and rapidly changing technology (Davenport, 2006). The HPWPs of performance evaluation, learning and development, and involvement in decision making could make employees to achieve higher job performance, thereby influencing the operation of project-based organisations. Therefore, the findings of our study support the previous studies that found HPWPs have positive effect on employees and organisations (such as Macky & Boxall, 2008; Patterson et al. 1997).

The findings have implications for both theory and practice. With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, there is surprisingly little empirical research that investigated HPWPs in project-based organisations in the literature. We have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated the aspects studied in this research to make straight forward comparisons. Therefore, the findings of our study make a contribution to the literature on project-based organisations. However, a considerable future research is necessary to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article. Yet, we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the practice, first, the findings suggest that learning and development practices lead to higher levels of job performance. The literature suggests that employees today have a much shorter cycle before their skills become obsolete (Edvinsson & Camp, 2005). Therefore, continuous learning and development programmes should be provided to equip employees with up-to-date knowledge and skills for them to perform their jobs effectively. The evaluation of the required capabilities by the employees and the provision of broad range of learning and development

activities will enhance employees' current as well as immediate future capabilities. Second, the findings suggest that performance evaluation practices strategically enhance job performance. The process of performance evaluation has characteristics that cater for both administrative and motivational purposes. Formalised job based performance evaluation with opportunities for two-way communication could guide individual to achieve a higher level of performance. Third, the findings suggest that employee involvement in decision-making enhance job performance. Project-based team work structure is commonly used by software development firms to allocate work assignments. Involvement of individual employees in the decision-making process could enhance their job performance. Hence, organisations should provide appropriate channels for employees to involve in the decision-making process. Finally, in project-based organisations HRM tasks are carried out by the HRM department, line managers, and by project managers (Huemann, 2010; Julian, 2008; Peterson, 2007; Schmid & Adams, 2008; Söderlund & Bredin, 2007). Yet, the literature suggests that the role of human resource function is high in the successful adoption of HPWPs (Murphy & Southey 2003). The human resource department should become an agent of change with the ability to develop, plan and implement HPWPs that have a link to higher levels of performance. In this regard, the encouragement, focus and direction the human resource function receives from the organisational leaders in implementing HPWPs would be invaluable.

Limitations and future research areas

The research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology; the study relied on self-reported data. Future studies can incorporate other HPWPs such as team work and knowledge sharing. Further, the respondents in our sample used ICT to perform day-to-day work tasks. Yet, we have not controlled variables such as the degree of ICT usage and frequency/duration of face-to-face meetings. Future research could incorporate such variables. Furthermore, future research studies in different samples that

compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data are necessary to validate the links proposed in this study. In such studies, questionnaire survey may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey.

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Figure

Figure 1: Research model

Tables

Table 1. Sample characteristics

<u>Individual characteristics</u>	
Age (in years):	
20-30	86.6%
31-40	13.4%
Gender:	
Male	63.8%
Female	36.2%
Highest level of education:	
Graduate	82.0%
Post-Graduate	18.0%
Experience (present workplace):	
Mean	3.66
S.D.	2.04
Experience (total):	
Mean	4.23
S.D.	2.31
<u>Team characteristics</u>	
Number of members in the present team:	
Less than 5	26.98%
5 to 10	40.00%
10 to 20	25.12%
More than 20	7.91%
Number of project managers for the present project life cycle:	
1	42.0%
2	28.8%
3	11.0%
More than 3	18.3%
Number of teams involved in the project:	
1	18.2%
2	17.8%
3 to 4	23.8%
More than 4	40.2%
<u>Firm characteristics</u>	
Years of business existence:	
Mean	12.23
S.D.	.42
Number of employees (present workplace):	
Mean	867.80
S.D.	344.05
Existence of HR dept/unit:	
Yes	60%
No	40%
If, HR dept/unit exists, the number of HR staff:	
Mean	20.13
S.D.	11.58
If, HR dept/unit does not exist, who handles HR work:	
Line management	42.34%
Project managers	24.32%
Administrative staff	27.03%
General manager	4.5%
Other	1.81%

Table 2. Summarised results of factor analysis – HPWPs

	Factor 1 Performance evaluation	Factor 2 Learning and Involvement development in decision- making	Factor 3
Your organisation provides specific examples of expected performance during performance review discussions	.679		
Performance feedback helps you to improve your performance	.816		
Often you get honest performance feedback during the review	.769		
Often you use the feedback on performance to plan your future career	.795		
Your organisation facilitates employees to acquire required information easily at anytime		.571	
Your organisation shares up-to-date information about competitors and industry trends with employees		.628	
Employees in your organisation openly discuss their mistakes in order to learn from them		.670	
Your organisation generally supports requests of its employees' for learning opportunities		.690	
Training sessions provided by your organisation help in improving your current job performance		.662	
Training sessions conducted by your organisation help in improving your future job performance		.489	
Your organisation uses two-way communication (such as suggestion systems, electronic bulletin boards or open meetings) to discuss organisational issues on a regular basis			.652
Teams in your organisation have the freedom to adapt their goals as needed			.668
Teams in your organisation revise their thinking as a result of group discussions			.529
Teams in your organisation are confident that the organisation will act on their recommendations			.831
Explained variation	38.16	19.56	9.23
Eigenvalue	5.62	3.34	1.15
Cronbach's alpha	.846	.773	.737

Table 3. Summarised results of factor analysis – job performance

	Job performance
You are always appreciated for the quality of your work	.805
You are the fastest at the work you do	.784
You are currently working at the best performance level	.754
You are willing to expend extra effort when it is needed	.616
Explained variation	55.25%
Eigenvalue	2.210
Cronbach's alpha	.721

Table 4. Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 Age	.53	.34	1										
2 Gender	.36	.48	.104	1									
3 Education	.49	.38	.238**	.048	1								
4 Experience – present workplace	3.66	2.04	.487**	.054	.234**	1							
5 Experience – total	4.23	2.31	.529**	.039	.260**	.569**	1						
6 Number of employees [†]	17.80	4.05	.052	.107	.060	.238**	.037	1					
7 Industry presence	12.23	.423	.090	.122	.050	.272**	.089	.991**	1				
8 Existence of HR dept.	.40	.492	.156*	.095	.108	.373**	.216**	.549**	.602**	1			
9 Performance evaluation	3.65	.72	.061	.022	.001	.006	.050	.188**	.184*	.021	1		
10 Learning and development	3.44	.57	.105	.013	.037	.088	.122	.077	.065	.000	.294**	1	
11 Involvement in decision-making	3.53	.76	.051	.102	.141*	.064	.003	.107	.137	.170*	.220**	.162*	1
12 Job performance	3.61	.51	.109	.074	.021	.041	.071	.084	.172	.104	.550**	.570**	.266**

** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). [†] Log transformed

Table 5. Summarized results - regression analysis

Step	Variable	β	R ²	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics		
					R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change
1	Age	.040	.038	.009	.038	.808	.596
	Gender	.079					
	Education	.043					
	Experience – present workplace	.006					
	Experience – total	.060					
	Number of employees	.052					
	Industry presence	.072					
	Existence of HR dept.	.017					
2	Age	.028	.483	.415***	.435	37.67	.000
	Gender	.084					
	Education	.038					
	Experience – present workplace	.009					
	Experience – total	.005					
	Number of employees	.034					
	Industry presence	.036					
	Existence of HR dept.	.020					
	Performance evaluation	.308***					
	Learning and development	.385***					
	Involvement in decision-making	.318***					

* p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001.

Table 6: Summary – results of hypotheses testing

Hypothesis	Result
H1	Supported (shown in Table 5)
H2	Supported (shown in Table 5)
H3	Supported (shown in Table 5)